

Advanced Post-Processing for Object Detection Dataset Generation

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Abstract. Fast acquisition and generation of training data is an important problem for the training of Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). Previous work using luminance keying for efficient training data acquisition achieves good results with very low effort, due to the high light absorption capabilities of the black background which enables keying through luminance instead of chroma. However, it does not reach real-world recording levels of performance. This paper significantly improves the achievable performance of luminance keying as evaluated for the use case of object detection. We introduce a novel post-processing pipeline incorporating a denoising diffusion probabilistic model (DDPM) to capitalize on luma-key recordings. First, we employ low rank adaptation (LoRA) to teach the recorded objects to a diffusion model. Second, we use Depth Anything to estimate the depth of the luma-key data. Third, utilizing ControlNet with depth estimates and Canny image filtering for guidance, we generate photo-realistic training images, using a wide range of relevant prompts, which increases model robustness in diverse environments. Applying the high quality masks of luminance keying, we get perfect ground truth for the object detection training. Extensive testing on the YCB-V object set demonstrates that our approach performs favorably compared to traditional techniques that require 3D meshes and material data, such as physically-based rendering or in-distribution dataset splits. Our proposed pipeline improves luminance keying to provide an efficient methodology for creating high-quality training datasets, facilitating the swift development and training of state-of-the-art DNNs for object detection, and is applicable to similar tasks, such as classification, and segmentation.

Keywords: Computer Vision · Machine Learning · Object Detection · Synthetic Data.

1 Introduction

Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) require large amounts of data for training, preventing their use in applications, where data might be sparse or hard to come by. Previous work [32] demonstrated the good performance of luminance-keying for data acquisition when using an inexpensive setup built upon a black cloth with strong light absorption properties, achieving results that are comparable

to much more involved data generation schemes, such as object scanning and (physically-based) rendering. While this luminance keying approach achieves satisfying results for many applications, there is still a noticeable gap compared to using real-world recordings of the target objects or training on physically-based renderings (PBR). The goal of our research is to reduce the margin between what can be achieved with the described low-cost luminance-keying approach and real-world recordings/PBR training, further closing the cost of training state-of-the-art 2D object detection models. Towards this goal we introduce a post-processing pipeline that takes the short recordings as proposed by luminance-keying as inputs and outputs high quality training data. Our processing utilizes the outstanding results of current DDPMs to generate high-fidelity realistic images, and incorporates the powerful extensions ControlNet [49] and LoRA [19] to guide their output towards generating data for detector training, applicable to industry use cases as in the ZDZW-project (<https://www.zdzw-project.eu>).

Our contribution extends luminance-keying with a post-processing pipeline to enable fast, geometry-model-free data acquisition for training high-performing 2D object detection models. We evaluate our approach using the widely-used YCB-V dataset of household objects [44]. We provide additional materials, such as trained LoRAs and LoRA training configurations, for reproducibility at <https://github.com/tpoellabauer/AdvancedFastDataAcquisition-ObjDetSeg>.

2 Related Work

2.1 Chroma- and Luminance-Keying

Chroma- and luminance-keying are well established techniques in cinematography and have recently been adopted to generate training data for machine learning [1,8,27,31,45]. Chroma keying traditionally suffers from color dependence, i.e. using a certain color for keying makes it difficult to depict subjects of similar color. In addition it suffers from effects such as color bleeding, reflections, refractions, and shadowing. Luminance-keying on the other hand does not suffer from these problems by virtue of using brightness for keying. In combination with a black background that absorbs most of the visible light spectrum, it can be used for fast data acquisition as described in detail in [32].

2.2 Generative Image Models

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs). GANs solve a min-max-problem between two networks, the generator, which tries to generate samples that the second network, the discriminator, can not distinguish from samples drawn from the real underlying distribution [14]. While GANs achieve high image quality, they are notoriously difficult to train and have problems with multi-modal feature distributions, as well as integrating language features. Ongoing work tried to solve all of these problems: Wasserstein GANs [2] improved training stability and

mitigated the problem of mode collapse and was further refined in [15]. Karras et al. [21] suggested a progressive growing scheme to increase the output resolution of GANs towards one Megapixel without training failure. StyleGAN introduced a second latent space for feature disentanglement as well as the use of adaptive instance normalization (ADAIn) inspired by style transfer literature to improve upon ProGAN [24] and was further improved in [25], dropping the progressive growing. [22] improved the results with limited data, while [23] presents an alias-free generator. [41] tackles the problem with diverse, multi-modal datasets and tries to scale the network to increase its expressiveness. GigaGAN [20] sets out to incorporate language features towards allowing text-to-image generation.

Denosing Diffusion Probabilistic Models (DDPM). DDPMs [18] are latent variable models that came to dominate the domain of generative image models, dramatically outperforming previous designs, such as the GAN. DDPMs are much easier to train compared to GANs: First, they repeatedly introduce noise to an image, continuously degrading the quality till it fully consists of noise. Subsequently, the model reverses the process, repeatedly removing noise to reconstruct the image content. It does so by calculating a score function, which directs towards areas of higher data likelihood with less noise.

A wide range of different models were introduced, such as DALL-E [36], DALL-E 2 [35], and DALL-E 3 [3], Imagen [40], and Stable Diffusion [38], each trying to improve in visual fidelity, fine-tune-ability, prompt alignment, and inference speed. Comprehensive surveys compare these and other designs in detail [7,47].

Control-ability and guidance of the diffusion process. A big part of the success of today’s generative vision models is to be found in the emergence of foundation models such as CLIP [34] and BLIP 2 [28], linking image features with natural language. Language is a powerful tool to communicate to the generative process the details of what it should produce. However, that alone is not sufficient guidance to achieve pixel-accurate ground truth labels for supervised machine learning. Works such as ControlNet [49] and T2i-adapter [30] allow for much stricter supervision of the generation process, leading the way to perfect labeling of generated images, by making the diffusion process follow the provided prior. Among the many image priors demonstrated are sketches, OpenPose key-point prediction [5], segmentation, Canny edges, and depth, to name a few, all of which can be combined into a single generation. Among those we find edges, following the Canny edge detection algorithm [4] and depth as especially useful for guaranteeing correct object placement in generated images. Monocular depth prediction algorithms produce plausible and quite accurate results in the domains of relative as well as metric depth estimation. Notable are Midas [37] and the recent Depth Anything [46].

Another direction of research investigates the possibilities to fine-tune large DDPMs to teach new concepts to the model without re-training the whole model. Notable works following this goal are Dreambooth [39], textual inversion [11], hypernetworks, and LoRA [19]. Dreambooth uses a small set of refer-

ence images to achieve subject recontextualization, the generation of new views preserving subject-specific key features. It does so by leveraging semantic priors and a class-specific prior preservation loss. Textual inversion introduces a unique word embedding to encode a new concept. The embedding is fed to the diffusion model and the optimization modifies the embedding instead of training the whole DDPM. LoRA introduces a small amount of additional weights to the network, and only trains these, while freezing the bigger part of the model. This leads to drastically reduced training times, compute and storage requirements. Hypernetworks, similar to LoRA, also manipulate the cross-attention module of the noise predicting UNet. Most importantly, the hypernetworks in context of Stable Diffusion are not to be confused with previously introduced [16]. Empirically hypernetworks seem to be less effective compared to Dreambooth, textual inversion, and LoRA. All of these approaches can be combined.

2.3 Distinction from similar Work

There is a long standing tradition to generate synthetic data for training of machine learning models. For a long time, most of these approaches leveraged variational autoencoders (VAE) or GANs. We will report a few of diffusion-based methods most similar to ours and explain how we differ from them.

DatasetDM [43] uses a two-stage pipeline to generate synthetic data. They adopt a common technique used with GANs, called inversion. Using what they term diffusion inversion, they extract latent codes, given less than 1% of the training data. This portion of training data needs to be labeled. With these codes they train a decoder to reconstruct the annotations. In a second step they can run the diffusion model and use their decoder to predict the labels. There are several important differences compared to our work: Our method follows a modular approach, which allows to switch out individual processing steps with improved algorithms, like swapping Midas-based depth prediction with Depth Anything. Theirs needs to re-train their decoder. We, by incorporating luminance-keying, get perfect object ground truth for free, they require at least some labeled examples, which they use to predict annotations for new samples. We are only concerned with guiding the model to follow our ground truth. Finally, they do not present instance-level object detection results with real-time capable object detectors. DiffusionDet [6] formulates the detection problem as part of the diffusion process, introducing a noise-to-box paradigm, very unlike our approach. [10] proposes to use controllable diffusion models for data augmentation in the use case of object detection. They generate visual priors (such as edges) by extracting them from labeled data and generate new data, similar to our idea. However, they do not use anything similar to our object encoding using LoRAs, giving us much more expressiveness, while they are limited to what their 2D input allows them to do. Nvidias FoundationPose [42] also utilizes a diffusion model to generate texture augmentations of objects, though also requires 3D meshes, which are used together with a physics engine and path tracing to generate their training data, leading to a much higher compute requirement than our proposed method, as well as needing object meshes.

Fig. 1: Overview of our proposed method. We use luminance-keying (images with black background) to quickly record ground truth data. Sampling from those recordings we train a LoRA to learn the object appearance. Next, we again sample from the luminance-keyed recordings, extract Canny edges, estimate depth with Depth Anything, filter the depth estimate with the luminance mask and generate new training samples by passing our image priors to ControlNet, together with our trained LoRA and a randomly sampled textual prompt.

3 Methodology

Following the approach of luminance-keying, we use their provided YCB-V-LUMA dataset [33] as input to our processing. By virtue of luminance-keying using the high light absorption background, we can easily extract the objects by thresholding. At this point simple augmentation procedures (cut and paste) achieve good results with low efforts [8,9]. We argue that we can achieve much better results by investing a little more resources, while still staying within the compute budget of a typical consumer GPU and within reasonable time constraints. Our two-stage method is illustrated in Figure 1.

3.1 LoRA Training

We propose to utilize the perfectly masked images provided by luminance-keying to learn a representation of our target objects within the diffusion model. The representation should learn texture, surface details, material, and overall shape of the object and allow to generate novel views of the objects within natural scenes. Following our research we argue that LoRAs are an easy to use, easy to train, and very inexpensive way to meet this requirement. We use LoRA to encode our objects, using 250 randomly sampled images per object from the approximately 1-minute long recordings found in YCB-V-LUMA. While LoRAs can represent multiple concepts, we train one LoRA per object. Using images sampled from the LUMA recordings we quickly converge to a powerful object appearance representation. For our training, instead of just updating the text encoder, we also train the convolutional layers in what is known as LoCon [26]. Some of the important parameters are the use of the prodigy [29] optimizer, which gave us consistently good results in our preliminary tests, with a weight decay of 0.01, decouple set to true, use of bias correction, an effective batch size of 4, a training dataset of 250 images and a training time of 30 epochs, which gives a total number of 1.875 optimizer steps. Training takes only a few minutes

Fig. 2: Sample images generated using our method. We see realistic lighting, shadows, reflection, and object placement (row 1). In row 2, we see that the model can create high quality variations of the object surface. Three caveats: There is a noticeable amount of images with surreal scene compositions (row 1, image 4, row 2 image 1 and 4), and the learned texture of the target objects sometimes transfers to the background (row 1, image 1). Finally, we note problems with reconstructing some texture details. Canny reduces the problem, but issues with text are a typical problem of generative models.

on a reasonable modern computer (tested on Nvidia RTX 3090). Equipped with the trained LoRAs we move on to the data generation. For reproducibility, we will publish our training configuration file with our trained LoRAs. Please feel free to check them out for more details.

3.2 Data Generation

The resulting LoRA allows us to generate new images of the target object and by itself tends to produce a large amount of suitable training images without additional guidance. However, we need bounding boxes to train an object detector and without additional guidance, we generate many images with undesired characteristics such as object deformations. Therefore, for every to-be-generated image, we construct a tuple $v = (rgb, mask, depth, edge, text, lora)$, where rgb is the image sampled from the short recordings, $mask$ is rgb with an applied threshold to get the object mask (using LAB color space we threshold based on the L-channel), $depth$ is the depth estimate of rgb , $edge$ is Canny edge filtering applied to rgb , $text$ is one of multiple on-the-fly constructed prompts, and $lora$ is the per-object trained LoRA. For a wide variation of scenes, we construct

Table 1: List of data processing methods, we considered, in computation-wise increasing order. LUMA only uses thresholding for post processing, while ALPHA also uses alpha blending with a natural images used as background. LUMA KEY is a more involved version of ALPHA, sampling multiple objects to create each training image. DIFFUSION is a set produced with our method.

Name	Description
LUMA (L)	Crops from recordings using luminance-keying [32]
ALPHA (A)	(L) placed on randomly selected images from the HQ-50k dataset using alpha-blending
LUMA KEY (LK)	A set of images following the processing as described in [32]
(A+LK+D)	Our mix of 20% A, 40% LK, and 40% D
DIFFUSION (D)	Diffusion generated images using our trained LoRAs and depth+Canny-guided ControlNet

each prompt by sampling from a list of relevant scene and object descriptions. Given a tuple v constructed as above, we use depth and edge information as image priors with ControlNet, the mask to construct bounding box labels for object detection, textual prompting for scene description, and LoRA to encode visual object details. Relative depth estimates are calculated using Depth Anything. In order to not unnecessarily restrict the novel image generation, we mask the depth prediction to only pass the object depth to ControlNet (by applying *mask* to *depth*), circumventing the otherwise often occurring result, that the object is estimated to stand upon a surface, which would restrict the freedom of the diffusor. As for the DDPM, we use Stable Diffusion 1.5.

3.3 Detector Training

For evaluation of our method, we create multiple training sets to show the influence of combining different kinds of data processing. The base datasets are listed in Table 1. For detector training, we followed the parameterization reported in [32], allowing for a fair comparison. That means we trained a YOLOX [12] model of size "tiny" with an image size of 512x512, half precision, a multiscale range of 13, and for a duration of 300 epochs. In line with [17], we freeze the backbone layers to reduce the impact of domain shift. All our experiments are initialized with COCO-pretrained weights.

4 Evaluation

We are interested in the performance of a YOLOX object detector when trained on data following different acquisition / generation procedures. First, we show samples of the data generated with our approach to give an impression of the achievable visual quality. Second, we give a short ablation study comparing the training success when using data following different generation procedures. Third, we will be discussing the quantitative results of our method in detail.

4.1 Qualitative Results

We report qualitative results in Figure 2. All in all we can generate high fidelity images depicting natural looking objects in various conditions, such as lighting differences, and scene compositions. Our biggest problem are some special kinds of textures. While complex patterns as found in the objects "bowl" or "wood block" do not pose a problem, our model is not capable of reconstructing intricate details for some textures, such as those containing text or depictions on household objects, such as the cracker box or the coffee can. Larger models like Stable Diffusion XL appear to be more adept in this regard, but they typically come with higher computational requirements, which is detrimental to our objective of fast training data acquisition.

4.2 Ablation Study

We evaluate the influence of combining different datasets in Table 2. As expected, training on the LUMA data without further post-processing leads to very poor results. The model seems to overfit on finding objects in front of black backgrounds and cannot generalize to real-world scenes. Swapping the black background with a randomly selected natural image using alpha blending (ALPHA) drastically improves performance. Training on our diffusion data (DIFF) without any data processing results in performance that falls between LUMA and ALPHA. We attribute this to the low visual overlap between the narrow scope of test images (indoor scenes) and our dataset. The test images often depict objects with significant occlusion, which we did not model explicitly in our dataset. The low performance of DIFF on its own should not be due to bad textures, as adding LUMA (perfectly depicting texture) does not yield significantly better results. Combining our data with ALPHA however does lift results noticeable above solely using ALPHA. We further obtain a slight performance bump by adding LUMA back into the mix. Following the processing of [32] - sampling multiple objects from luminance-keyed recordings, placing them randomly on natural images, while allowing for overlap to simulate occlusion and applying gaussian blur and gaussian noise (LK) - leads to significantly improved results with the caveat that this dataset has 5-times as many object instances (5 per image compared to only one per image). To get the best of all worlds, we mix our newly generated diffusion images with images following the processing of the luminance-keying paper and ALPHA images, using 20.000 randomly selected images from ALPHA, and 40.000 each from LK and DIFF. Comparing the results of LK and (ALPHA+LK+DIFF) after 100, as well as after 300 epochs (both sets have 100.000 images), we see a noticeable improvement in AR and especially AP for our mix, whereas LK's performance does not improve further.

4.3 Quantitative Results

All experiments are validated on an in-distribution disjoint split of disjoint object poses i.e. the set of object poses in the train and validation sets are disjoint.

Table 2: Ablation results when adding different data sources to the dataset and training for a fixed number of epochs (EP) without additional data augmentation and without early stopping. LUMA represents the masked recordings (objects on a perfectly black background). ALPHA in addition blends the cropped objects onto randomly selected backgrounds taken from the HQ-50k dataset [48]. DIFFUSION is our set of diffusion-generated images. LK is the dataset of 100.000 images as provided by the luminance-keying paper [32]. Details on the datasets are to be found in Table 1. Relevant metrics are AR and AP (higher is better). Tested on the real-world recordings provided by BOP.

EP	LUMA	ALPHA	LK [32]	DIFFUSION (OURS)	AR	AP
100	✓				2.01	0.93
100		✓			18.05	8.38
100				✓	14.06	7.39
100	✓			✓	14.88	7.75
100		✓		✓	19.45	10.09
100	✓	✓		✓	21.38	11.12
100			✓		47.74	25.53
300			✓		46.56	24.27
100		✓	✓	✓	49.57	29.85
300		✓	✓	✓	54.56	32.34

With in-distribution we mean that the validation split, used for early-stopping, is a disjoint split of data, coming from the same data generating process as the training data. We reason that a good data generation process also needs to be able to inform the model when to stop training and generalize well to real-world test data. All testing is done on 900 images sampled from the official BOP test set for YCB-V, depicting the real-world recordings. The relevant metrics are average Recall (AR) and average precision (AP). AR measures the ability of an object detection algorithm to correctly identify objects of interest in an image. It calculates the average percentage of true positive detections over different levels of detection confidence or intersection over union (IoU) thresholds. AP quantifies the precision of object detections by considering both the number of true positive detections and the number of false positive detections. It is determined by calculating the area under the precision-recall curve.

Based on our ablation study we build a training set by mixing images from three different generation processes: 20% A, 40% LK, and 40% D. For a fair comparison with the baseline, we also decide to sample a total of 100.000 images. Please note, because with LK there are 5 objects per image, we have a noticeable smaller number of object instances in our set. As with the original paper on luminance-keying, all of our data can be generated fully-automatic without manual effort. All training parameters are in line with [32]. We report results of our method in Table 3.

Table 3: AR and AP (higher is better) of all evaluated data sources. All are tested against real recordings from the YCB-V [44]. As expected, we see the best results when training on the train split of the real data (RECORDINGS) or the physically simulated 3D scenes (PBR). Our advanced post-processing (OURS) noticeably reduces the gap between alpha blended images using luminance-keying (LUMA) and a set of diverse real-world RECORDINGS. The baseline (LUMA) and OURS are highlighted.

DATA SOURCE:	PBR [32]	RECORDINGS [32]	LUMA [32]	OURS
002_master_chef_can	77.07 / 62.13	79.00 / 73.76	71.97 / 46.17	70.90 / 59.51
003_cracker_box	66.44 / 20.65	62.89 / 43.34	48.53 / 20.90	54.22 / 20.03
004_sugar_box	66.80 / 48.36	61.63 / 49.54	69.07 / 52.64	74.27 / 62.36
005_tomato_soup_can	69.71 / 55.53	75.09 / 70.21	61.80 / 29.17	67.13 / 51.16
006_mustard_bottle	87.60 / 78.20	91.27 / 88.82	84.13 / 79.90	87.20 / 81.25
007_tuna_fish_can	78.83 / 70.77	83.77 / 79.35	73.30 / 60.97	77.47 / 67.60
008_pudding_box	56.60 / 04.48	48.93 / 06.64	27.07 / 00.92	36.13 / 01.18
009_gelatin_box	78.40 / 71.21	74.27 / 65.41	16.27 / 00.55	58.00 / 17.70
010_potted_meat_can	64.98 / 37.64	59.60 / 54.23	52.93 / 26.22	54.13 / 22.68
011_banana	70.87 / 54.24	61.40 / 50.18	55.33 / 48.64	61.93 / 55.25
019_pitcher_base	77.33 / 55.57	84.22 / 80.89	06.44 / 00.32	60.98 / 41.92
021_bleach_cleanser	60.43 / 43.58	71.00 / 61.31	63.10 / 54.61	58.63 / 51.47
024_bowl	73.07 / 46.75	63.13 / 56.90	55.60 / 14.44	66.60 / 53.34
025_mug	74.13 / 58.14	71.93 / 67.35	45.08 / 14.37	53.87 / 16.00
035_power_drill	44.43 / 13.26	54.23 / 43.72	54.23 / 13.23	57.43 / 14.16
036_wood_block	65.73 / 24.57	50.80 / 34.06	57.07 / 17.32	52.93 / 25.64
037_scissors	20.80 / 05.48	06.40 / 01.96	03.73 / 00.52	01.87 / 00.39
040_large_marker	62.00 / 47.65	63.33 / 56.73	31.47 / 05.42	49.47 / 13.60
051_large_clamp	69.80 / 47.43	32.80 / 06.40	36.53 / 17.75	49.47 / 20.62
052_extra_large_clamp	45.87 / 07.21	35.87 / 09.80	09.07 / 00.29	14.47 / 01.04
061_foam_brick	72.93 / 55.61	76.27 / 67.82	54.40 / 05.22	36.27 / 01.54
AVERAGE	65.89 / 43.26	62.28 / 50.88	46.56 / 24.27	54.45 / 32.31

The results show that our dataset significantly outperforms in comparison to original luminance-keying. After training for 100 epochs the difference was not as pronounced (49.57 / 29.85 vs. 47.74 / 25.53), but we can see a continuous improvement with ongoing training, whereas the baseline does no longer improve with more training (47.74 / 25.53 after 100 epochs vs. 46.56 / 24.27 with 300 epochs). Especially the gain according to the AP metric using our approach is significant. Also, some objects, such as object 19, the "pitcher", improve dramatically. That might have to do with the fact, that originally this object was opaque and blue, while it is white and semi-transparent in the currently available YCB-V object set. Our diffusion images depict a much larger variation of appearance, which might help the network generalize to different colors. We do note a drop in performance on some objects, most notably the "foam brick". This might be due to the fact, that our diffusion model does not always reconstruct the object perfectly. In this specific case, the original object has a smooth

surface with 3 holes. Our model tends to reconstruct the surface correctly, but generates objects with more and fewer holes repeatedly, making it more difficult for our detector to learn the true shape. Lastly, the above mentioned problem with text and some textures, seems not to reduce our performance. Comparing some of the concerned objects (e.g. "master chef can", "cracker box", "bleach cleanser") are either performing better with our method, or do not lose much according to our metrics.

4.4 Discussion

We showed that including images generated with our method improves the training success as measured by average recall and average precision. We argue that, while the data on its own is not sufficient to reach state-of-the-art performance, adding it to the mix makes the trained model better at generalization by increasing the variation of object appearances and (often) realistic object placement. Textures, for instance, often change color while still staying true to the original object material and introduce some domain randomization. Furthermore, they are not perfectly reproduced, pushing the model to not rely too much on it as an image queue. That in turn disincentivises overfitting to texture, which is commonly happening with CNNs [13]. Most importantly, all our processing is fully automated, thereby maintaining the ease-of-use of the original paper describing luminance-keying.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper addresses the challenge of fast, model-free acquisition and generation of training data for DNNs in the context of object detection. While previous work using luminance keying achieved good results with low effort, it fell short of in-distribution levels of performance. This paper introduces a novel post-processing pipeline that incorporates a denoising diffusion probabilistic model to improve the achievable performance of luminance keying. By employing LoRA to teach the recorded objects to a diffusion model, estimating depth using Depth Anything, and leveraging ControlNet with Canny edge filtering and depth images for guidance, we generate photo-realistic training images with a wide range of prompts. This approach leads to more robust model performance in diverse environments, and the high-quality masks generated through luminance keying provide perfect ground truth for object detection training. Our evaluation demonstrates that our approach noticeably improves the results achievable with luminance keying in the context of object detection, enabling the creation of high-quality training datasets in an automated, controlled, and reproducible manner.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

Acknowledgement This research has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme in the course of the ZDZW project under grant agreement No 101057404. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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